

Deliverable Report D7.3

Organisation of the Kick-off Meeting & Initial Project Documentation and Resources

Project & Programme Information	
Project Acronym	INSIGHT
Project Full Name	Integrated Models for the Development and Assessment of High Impact Chemicals and Materials
Grant Agreement No.	101137742
Work Programme	Horizon Europe Cluster 4 - Digital, Industry and Space
Call	RESILIENT VALUE CHAINS 2023 (HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01)
Topic & Title	HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-22: Integrated approach for impact assessment of safe and sustainable chemicals and materials
Instrument	Horizon Europe – Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Project Start Date	01 January 2024
Duration	48 months

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Deliverable Information	
Work Package	WP7
Deliverable Number	7.3
Associated Task	Task 7.1
Type ¹	R
Dissemination Level ²	PU
Version	V01
Actual Submission Date	28.6.2024
Contractual Submission Date	30.6.2024
Lead author (organisation)	TAU
Contributors	
Reviewers	ULEI, WH

Version	Date	Changes made	By	Sent to	Purpose
0.1	31.5.2024	Draft version	TAU	ULEI, WH	Partner contribution
0.2	16.6.2024	Review	ULEI, WH		Review
0.3	18.6.2024	Review	all	INSIGHT email list	Review
1.0	26.6.2024	Finalisation & Submission	TAU	EC	Submission

¹ R= Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports); DEM = Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC = Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA =Data sets, microdata, etc.; DMP = Data management plan; ETHICS = Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY = Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER = Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

² PU = Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Acronyms Listed in this Document

EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
DESCA	Model Consortium Agreement
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
AI	Artificial Intelligence

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Executive Summary

This deliverable provides information about the project Kick-off meeting and gives an overview of the initial INSIGHT documentation and resources. The agenda of the Kick-off meeting is presented as well as the location, number of participants, and main purpose. The project documentation section consists of a list of key documents and a brief description of the project team repository and the use of the group email list. Project resources are presented in the last chapter.

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I Organisation of the INSIGHT Kick-off meeting

The INSIGHT Kick-off meeting was held on 15-16 February 2024 in Helsinki, Finland. The project started in January 2024 and the Kick-off meeting was designed to create alignment between everyone involved in the project. Each project partner organisation and the key persons were introduced at the meeting. Project Officer Dr. Antonios Konstantas also participated in the beginning of the meeting and gave an online presentation about the project rules and EC regulations. A total of 36 people attended the Kick-off meeting, 11 online and 25 face-to-face.

The detailed meeting agenda was provided to all project partners before the meeting. The two-day meeting consisted of:

- Partner presentations
- Greeting from the Project Officer
- Financial issues
- General discussion about the consortium agreement, next meetings, scientific advisory board, upcoming events
- WP leader presentations and break out room discussion

The minutes of the meeting and all presentations are available on the project internal repository. The detailed agenda of the Kick-off meeting is presented in the attachment I.

I.1 Meeting management

Regular project meetings will be held to support project management, communication, collaboration, and knowledge transfer within the work packages and consortium. Meetings may be face-to-face or virtual (using Zoom, Teams or any other suitable virtual meeting platform).

2 Initial project documentation

During the first six months of the INSIGHT project processes and documentations have been developed to manage project lifecycle. These documents and processes define activities, procedures and guidelines to be followed by the project partners. Documents and instructions are available to project partners in the project team repository.

Initial project documentation:

- Grant Agreement no. 101137742
- Consortium Agreement (DESCA model)
- Deliverable template
- Internal financial reporting template
- Contact list
- Presentation template
- Meeting notes

Coming documentation:

- Stakeholder database
- Project Quality Management Plan
- Risk Assessment Plan
- INSIGHT Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy
- Project Internal Ethical Guideline

The internal deliverable review process description and the internal milestone verification process descriptions have been provided to the project partners.

3 Project Team Directory/Repository

An electronic project folder was set up to act as a repository for all working documents. The folder is used not only for the exchange of working documents, but also for storing final and validated reports or deliverables, work packages, meeting documents, and other valuable information produced or collected during the project. The folder is accessible only to consortium members and authorised individuals. As a general rule, content should not be shared with parties outside the project.

4 Project email list

To support the internal communication and information flow, a project mailing list has been set up for all consortium members. The mailing list [insight\(at\)lists.tuni.fi](mailto:insight(at)lists.tuni.fi) is intended for any general communication of the project that concerns a majority of the members. Any

member of the mailing list can send a message to the mailing list. The coordinator is responsible for managing the mailing list and keeping the list of mailing list subscribers up-to-date.

5 Resources

Project resources, such as people, equipment, budget, time and knowledge are the components required to successfully deliver this project.

The capacity of the participants and the consortium as a whole is described in the INSIGHT Grant Agreement. The INSIGHT consortium brings together scientists from 20 partners with high quality research on the topic and with diverse backgrounds in chemical safety assessment, LCA, socio-economic studies, regulatory toxicology, environmental and innovation studies, science and technology, data science, AI and software development.

Project resources have been allocated to each partner to cover person-months and other costs required to fulfil the agreed responsibilities. Project budget is available in the Grant Agreement Annex 2 “Estimated budget for the action”. Details of the project schedule are presented in the Gantt chart, also available in the INSIGHT Grant Agreement.

ANNEX A1 – Kick-off meeting agenda

INSIGHT In-person Kick-Off Meeting

Date: 15th–16th February 2024

Place: Clarion Hotel Helsinki, Meeting room "Crusell" (2nd floor)

Virtual: <https://tuni.zoom.us/j/61800710981>

15th February

- 09:00 – 09:10** Introduction – Dario Greco
09:10 – 09:25 Greetings of the project Officer Dr. Antonios Konstantas
09:25 – 09:35 WP7 – Financial & reporting – Hanna Hastbäcka
09:35 – 10:05 Partners presentation – 1 slide 3 minutes each partner
- 1 TAU MET- Tampere University
 - 1 TAU SOC- Tampere University
 - 2 NovaM- Novamechanics
 - 3 NTUA- National Technical University of Athens
 - 4 ULEI– Leiden University
 - 5 LIST– Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology
 - 6 MUI– The medical University of Innsbruck
 - 7 WH– Warrant Hub
 - 8 UPO– University of Eastern Piedmont
 - 9 AUTH– Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
 - 10 AIST– Acumenist

10:05 – 10:15 Break

10:15 – 10:45 Partners presentation – 1 slide 3 minutes each partner

- 11 GRA– Graphenea
- 12 7P9– Seven Past Nine
- 13 EVO– Evonik Operations GmbH
- 14 SOLVAY– Solvay
- 15 EMPA– Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology
- 16 UNC– The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill
- 17 HU– Hanyang University
- 18 CNPEM– Brazilian Center for Research in Energy and Materials

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19 LTU – La Trobe University

20 UoB – The University of Birmingham

10:45 – 11:30 Discuss next meetings, SAB, Special issue, Deliverable Reviewers, MaterialWeek discussion (f2f WP leaders meeting?)

11:30 – 12:00 Consortium agreement update, governance structure, affiliate entity for NovaM

12:30 – 13:30 Lunch

13:30 – 17:00 WP break out rooms to kick off work.

19:00 Working dinner at Restaurant Savotta (address: Aleksanterinkatu 22, 00170 Helsinki)

16th February

WP leaders' presentations – summary of break out room discussion

09:00 – 09:30 WP1

09:30 – 09:40 WP2

09:40 – 09:55 WP3

09:55 – 10:10 Break

10:10 – 10:20 WP4

10:20 – 10:30 WP5

10:30 – 10:45 WP6

10:45 – 12:30 Discussion and wrap-up

12:30 Lunch

14:00 – 18:00 Informal future planning and networking, bi-lateral collaborations, etc.

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